

EFFECT OF COOPERATIVE SOCIETIES ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN EKITI STATE

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Abstract: The study examined the effect of cooperative societies on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Ekiti State with a special reference to Ado Local Government Area. It also examined the effect of financial services on business performance of SMEs, determine effect of non-financial services on business performance of SMEs, analyse the effect of membership on business performance of SMEs and investigate the effect of patronage of cooperative societies on business performance of SMEs in Ekiti State. The study employed primary sources of data, the primary sources was through fifty self-administered questionnaires of which ninety were retrieved and analysed using multiple regression model. The study revealed that financial services, non-financial services, membership and patronage of cooperative societies positively and significantly affect business performance of SMEs in Ekiti State. Based on the discovery, it was concluded that cooperative societies have positive and significant effect on business performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Ekiti State.

Keywords: Cooperative Societies; Business Performance; Small and Medium Scale Enterprises; Financial Services; Membership.

1.0 Introduction

In a cooperative society, producers, customers, employees, and citizens all work together to promote thrift, distribute wealth and power fairly, and advertise and sell their goods. The main goal of this business strategy is to cut out the middleman, increasing member profit margins and lowering the cost of selling products made by members (Dogarawa, 2010; Adeoye, 2015). Numerous cooperative organizations have emerged in Nigeria since the advent of modern cooperatives in the country's mid-1930s, each of which is struggling to promote social and economic development in its neighborhood (FMA&RD, 2002). Cooperative enterprises must be profitable and long-lasting. Without initially reforming the business sector to provide for its appropriate expansion, it will be impossible to achieve this long-term aim (Agbenyegah, 2013; Maclean, Jagannathan, & Sarvi, 2013).

Small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) account for 96% of all businesses in Nigeria and generate 49% of the country's GDP, according to statistics. The majority of micro, small, and medium-sized companies (MSMEs) were owned by lone proprietors (73%), followed by partnerships (6%), religious organizations (5%), private liability institutions (14%) and other types of businesses (1%). (PWCs MSME Survey, 2020). The majority of

company owners in Nigeria are sole proprietors who operate the micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises that are crucial to the nation's economic development, job creation, and social cohesion (Okike & Anyasodor, 2019). Cooperative societies have influenced the financing of small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) (OECD, 2015). This is due to the fact that even the most devoted entrepreneurs may have difficulties obtaining financing from traditional financial institutions. Because cooperative organizations have the built-in ability to defend members' interests, they have been able to investigate using private funds to promote corporate growth (Bakare, & Akinbode, 2016). The effect of cooperatives on the development of small and medium-sized businesses in Nigeria has not been thoroughly studied, despite the fact that they offer members better alternatives to traditional banking services like regular savings, business finances, short- and long-term loans, mentoring, education, and entrepreneurial training, as well as the purchase and sale of goods at competitive prices (Nembhard, 2014; Oluyombo, 2013). Nigeria has historically relied heavily on cooperatives and thrift institutions to support and develop the nation's small business community (Ademilua, 2017). A cooperative's primary goal is to improve the financial health of its members and the companies they jointly control by offering a variety of marketing and financial services.

Amazingly, despite the best efforts of the government and others, Nigeria's cooperative organizations have underperformed lately. The demise of the company has been attributed to a number of factors, including inadequate management, a lack of infrastructure (especially in the form of roads and power), a lack of technical skill, restricted access to the global market, and ineffectual regulatory agencies. When these fundamental infrastructures are maintained and fully functional, they play a critical role in promoting corporate development and growth, which helps societies and economies (Nwangugu, 2012; Nwoji & Oluwalaiye, 2012). Most cooperative groups had lost their motivation and sluggishness as a result of the neglect of these facilities; others had even dissolved as a result of the expensive expense of maintaining operations. Cooperative societies need the aforementioned fundamentals in addition to many more in order to prosper in the current economic climate and to successfully compete with worldwide rivals. In light of the aforementioned, several researchers have examined cooperatives in Lagos and their effects on economic growth, the function of cooperatives as a vehicle for entrepreneurship, the characteristics of successful entrepreneurs, and the effectiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (Dogarawa, 2020; Jiboye, et al., 2020; Oladunjoye et al., 2019). (SMEs). This paper has been written to close the gap.

2.0 Literature Review

Cooperative Society

Cooperative societies, a distinct kind of PEO, have been routinely used for decades to reduce waste and save resources. People are shown to see society as an asset that they must invest in, safeguard, and oversee for their own financial gain. In contrast to prizes based on ownership in connection to other essential individual business structures, the advantages for customers are based on consumption. Buyers' involvement in the cooperative's procurement or trading activities generates dividends, which are redistributed to the customers in direct proportion to their spending (Barton, 1989). The purpose of a cooperative society is twofold: to provide economic and social

support to its members (Adedayo et al, 2020). One way to look about cooperative societies is as the archetypal paradigm of a group of individuals working together to create and manage a business. According to Nembhard (2014), this action was taken because conventional investments were unable to meet certain market needs. As a result, the fundamental impetus behind the development of cooperative groups was the advancement of members' individual interests. Savings and credit cooperatives were introduced to much of Africa by missionaries from outside the region (Mwelukilwa, 2001).

The modern cooperative industry in Nigeria may be traced back to 1935, when Strickland's government officially recognized a feasibility study on setting up cooperatives in Nigeria (Agbo & Chidebelu, 2010). Since then, cooperatives in Nigeria have developed, and the nation currently has a three-level structure, from the most fundamental, grassroots cooperative societies to the more advanced, specialized tertiary cooperative societies. Cooperative societies in Nigeria were made legal by new laws that took effect in 1935. In 1937, the Gbedun Cooperate Producer Marketing Organization became the first indigenous cooperative organization in the United States. There were many more cooperatives that followed, but in 1967 the Cooperative Federation of Nigeria (CFN) was formed to serve as the country's governing body for cooperatives. This entity is housed inside the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development. In an effort to boost the economy, the government of Nigeria's Osun State has registered nearly 24,000 cooperatives as of 5 July 2017. The Ministry of Commerce, Cooperatives, and Empowerment is responsible for regulating cooperative societies in the State. The state of Osun's Ministry of Commerce, Investment, and Cooperatives is in charge of a wide range of responsibilities, including the registration and administration of cooperatives, the provision of credit to residents through loans and empowerment programs, the regulation of commerce, investment, and other lawful state-sanctioned activities, and the collection of taxation, fees, and other legal levies.

Cooperatives Societies and SMEs Advancement

The literature so far, including that of Wanyama (2015), reveals a link between the rise of cooperative organizations and the expansion of small and medium-sized enterprises. The study's emphasis on the benefits of cooperative society membership, such as access to more forgiving loan conditions, more fair profit sharing, and funding for community facilities like parks and libraries, likely contributed to this effect. Cooperative groups have the potential to boost economic development by addressing market imperfections, according to studies (Deller, Hoyt, Hueth & SundaramStukel, 2009). Effiom argues that cooperative societies have substantial impacts on national development because they not only carry out developmental activities like agriculture, transportation, and credit creation, but also serve as a catalyst for reducing poverty through the economic and social advancement of their members and employees (2014). In addition to paying taxes, members of cooperative societies also give back to their neighborhoods by investing in infrastructure projects, providing fair wages to employees, and minimizing their negative impact on the natural world (Nembhard, 2014).

Challenges by the faced Cooperative Societies in Nigeria

Cooperatives are used by people all over the world as a method of doing commerce. Cooperatives might confront challenges in any nation. Anyanwuocha (2011) listed five primary challenges faced by cooperative organizations.

Some of these issues include: difficulty in hiring competent management; inadequate financial resources; cooperative leaders who embezzle money; the use of cooperative resources for political ends; and the avoidance of taxation on cooperative profits. According to Akanle, Omotara, and Busari, cooperative societies in Nigeria face competition from other financial institutions (2014). This is due to the fact that there are several other means of securing capital for a company, and that other types of banking and finance might give advantages equal to or greater than those offered by cooperatives. Other problems, such as loan defaulting (delinquency), irregularities in loan repayment, and a poor saving culture of some members, are mentioned by Gbadeyan (2001), and are attributed to the relaxation of control in certain cooperative organizations. The election procedure in Nigerian cooperative societies places a higher value on the number of shares and total savings than on the experience and level of education of board members, both of which are concerns for the sector as a whole (Akanle, Omotara & Busari, 2014).

Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

Since the late 1940s, developed nations have been using the SME idea as a means of fostering economic growth and industrialization (OECD, 2004). Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are defined differently from country to country based on a number of criteria, including the significance of SMEs to the economy and the policies and programs implemented by the agencies and organizations entrusted with supporting their development. In a nation like Nigeria, which is still developing, a business that would be deemed little in the United States, Canada, or Japan can be regarded medium or even gigantic. Also, different organizations and developing institutions have different policy agendas that influence how they define a small or medium-sized firm (SME) (Etuk, Etuk & Michael, 2014).

According to Ikpor, Nnadu, and Itumo (2017), SMEs include a broad spectrum of enterprise sizes and kinds involved in a diverse array of economic pursuits. A wide variety of businesses are included here, from those owned by artisans who create local agricultural implements to those who run coffee shops, tailor shops, iron foundries, roadside mechanic shops, a small transportation company, an internet cafe, a small engineering or software firm, and a medium-sized auto parts manufacturer. There are a number of SMEs that, depending on their objectives, focus on either the domestic or global market. The people who own them may be dirt poor or filthy rich, and they could live anywhere in the globe. No universally accepted definition of "small business" exists (SMEs). The precise meaning of this phrase is context-dependent and may vary from nation to country. That's because every country's political and economic climate is unique (as explained by Etuk et al, 2014 above). For instance, the Nigerian Small and Medium Industries Equity Investment Scheme (SMIEIS) of 1998 designated SMEs as organizations with an initial investment of N1.5 million and N200 million. So, this total includes working capital but excludes the cost of the actual property. A small or medium-sized enterprise (SME) is defined as an establishment with 10 or less and no more than 300 total employees by the Nigerian National Council on Industry (Udechukwu, 2003).

The definition of a small or medium-sized enterprise (SME) given by Ikpor et al. (2014) is a company with less than 250 employees and annual revenues of less than €50 million. Additionally, the corporation required that its

minority stake in any other companies be less than 25%. A medium-sized company typically employs 100 to 300 people and earns \$15 million to \$25 million per year (World Bank, 2006). A small firm has less than 50 employees and annual revenues of less than \$3 million, as defined by the World Bank. Companies were considered small if they had ten workers or less and total yearly sales of less than \$100,000. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined by Etuk et al. (2014) as having annual sales of up to \$500,000. In 1990, the federal government allocated this sum specifically. Their original investments were less than two million naira, or five million naira including the price of the landed property, according to the definition. As a result, there is no universally accepted definition of SMEs; instead, it varies greatly depending on the nature of the firms in question and the location of their primary operations (Umar, 1997).

Businesses of various shapes and sizes may be found in the SME sector. There are two primary types of small and micro enterprises, those that are growth-oriented and those that are managed on a shoestring budget to sustain just the proprietors and a few part-time staff. Almost all SMEs in the world's poorest countries are barely making ends meet. On the other side, growth-oriented businesses are those that put an emphasis on new product development and geographical expansion via mergers and acquisitions. Companies that fit this description often participate in growing industries (Ikpor et al, 2017).

Theoretical Review

Social Capital Theory

Robert Putnam's ideas are most often linked to the concept of social capital (1993, 2000). Due to the prevalence of unsecured microfinance loans, the notion of social capital has emerged as a key player in the ongoing discussion about how to alleviate poverty. Natural capital, physical or manufactured capital, and human capital are the three types of capital that Ismawan (2000) says have traditionally been prioritized in attempts to decrease poverty. Their riches and economic success are the foundations of countries, but they fail to recognize the importance of the poor's ability to network and organize for progress. To make this dish, you need social capital (Kamusaala, 2016). Social capital, as defined by Rakodi (2002), comprises of the rules, norms, duties, reciprocity, and trust that are inherent in social connections, social structures, and the institutional organization of society, and which allow its members to attain both individual and community goals. To be considered "capital," social interactions must provide transferable resources (such trust or knowledge) that individuals may rely upon in the short term. Mutual aid is built via the contributions of persons who are not connected. We need trust, but we also need compassion, networks, generosity, and a will to address problems that affect everyone. Joining an association might help you build friendships that are stronger and more mutually beneficial. One recent study argues that social capital may be used as collateral in microfinancing (Kamusaala, 2016). According to the definition provided by Aliyu and Umaru (2016), microfinance is "the provision of financial services such as credits, savings, micro-leasing, micro-insurance, entrepreneurship development, promotion of investment, and payment transfer to economically active poor and low-income household in order to enable them to engage in income generating activities to enable them to escape poverty and/or expand/grow small businesses." Every culture has its own norms and practices when it comes to helping the needy.

Esusu, the Nigerian practice of frugality, is well-known. Microsavings accounts, revolving loans, and other forms of credit are all on the table. Nigeria is home to some of the first examples of microfinancing. Traditional microfinance firms provide access to credit for persons with low incomes in both rural and urban settings. Most of them are members of so-called "revolving savings and loan groups," or SHGs (ROSCAs). Cooperatives and other forms of collective savings may qualify as microfinance organizations (Imoisi & Opara, 2014; Alani & Sani, 2014). It is generally agreed that group lending tactics are the most efficient way to reach the poorest individuals who may benefit from microfinance. Group lending practices, such as those utilized by Dakkada Multi-purpose Cooperative Society, seem to be more successful with clients who take out smaller loans. Among the many reasons why social capital is so well-liked by members of rural Nigerian cooperatives is that the feeling of belonging or trust one gets from participating in DMPCS cannot be purchased. It is believed that free social capital aids SDGS by lowering poverty rates, empowering women, increasing access to healthcare and education, and bolstering economic stability. An understanding of the role social capital plays in the context of DMPCS's people-centered development activities is crucial. Because of the confidence among its members, it can continue to operate, remain cohesive, and endure with little to no outside help. The theory presents an argument for integrating qualitative and quantitative methods to investigate the link between the DMPCS and SDGS poverty alleviation factors (such as government assistance for small companies, access to financial capital, and women's engagement in the local economy).

Theory of Credit Rationing

The famous Stiglitz-Weiss (1981) model inspired the concept of credit limitation. The issue of banks refusing to provide new lines of credit to clients in financial distress is highlighted, as is the reality that these borrowers are often willing to accept a higher interest rate. DMPCS is able to make small, interest-free loans to its members, who are also considered borrowers, since it is aware that creditworthy borrowers are unable to get financing from regular banking institutions. The economic justification for DMPCS' intervention strategy can be found in the credit rationing literature, which goes beyond identifying the challenges posed by lending to low-income borrowers as members to include those without sources of income who are willing to engage in productive ventures under supervision. According to economic theory, financial resources are required for DMPCS members to engage in entrepreneurial and agricultural pursuits.

Empirical Review

The features of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) that favor government cooperative research and development funding were studied by Hyoungh, Chul, and Seung-Pyo (2016) for the Korean context. Examining how government policy affects the functioning of small and medium-sized businesses in Korea is the primary focus of this study. The research uses a secondary data source and employs decision tree and discrimination analysis on a subset of Korean businesses. This study's findings confirm that government agencies' policy enactment is geared toward speedy monitoring of the existence of small and medium-sized businesses and at alleviating the practical issues these businesses face. According to the findings, SMEs in the nation would benefit greatly from having ready access to the tools they need to function efficiently.

Using Odukpani as a case study, Ebong, Eteng, and Ekpo (2017) explored the potential of cooperative societies as an approach for fostering management competence among small enterprises in Cross River State's rural areas. In this research, Analysis of Variance is used to examine a single hypothesis. This investigation makes use of an ex-post facto research strategy. In systematic empirical inquiry, known as "ex-post facto," the scientist does not have direct control over the independent variables, since they are not possible to be manipulated. One hundred forty participants served as the study's sample size (140). There were seven (7) Wards/Villages with cooperative organizations, and twenty (20) people were chosen from each. To conduct this study, we employed a random sample method. The questionnaire was used to gather information for this investigation. Participation in cooperative societies was shown to have a positive effect on the growth of business management skills in Odukpani's rural villages.

In their 2017 article "The Role of Cooperative Society on Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise in Nigeria: Challenge and Way Forward," Nwankwo, Ewuim, and Asoya explored this question. The research looked at a claim about how far small and medium-sized businesses in Nigeria had come, and it argued for the elements that have an impact on that growth. The study used a simple regression analysis to investigate the elements that contribute to the success of SMEs in Nigeria. Cooperative societies that helped SMEs develop their projects were found to be the answer to the SMEs' problems, according to the research. In addition, the study's findings confirmed that cooperative societies aid SMEs in business financing by offering them interest-free loans to fund their operations. Finding that small and medium-sized businesses may rely on cooperative finance to keep their doors open, the research suggested that the federal government increase its support for cooperative society survival.

Small and medium-sized businesses have been the focus of an investigation by Zacheus and Omoseni (2018) on their effect on the growth of the Nigerian economy. Primary data were collected and the study period was from 2006 to 2015. Over the course of the study, one hundred and fifty (150) individuals were asked to fill out questionnaires. In order to determine whether or not the test variable was statistically significant at the 5% level of significance, the research used chi-square analysis. Small and medium-sized businesses in Ekiti were shown to have a positive correlation with the state's poverty rate. More than that, the research determined that the poverty rate in Ekiti state has increased by 57%. The findings of this study suggest that interest rates on loans made to small and medium-sized businesses should be capped by government regulation.

Godwin and Ikechukwu (2018) look at what affects people's decision to join cooperatives in Nigeria. In this study, we used a research questionnaire to collect first-hand information from eighty (80) participants. The descriptive method of data analysis was used to show the statistical distribution of the variables in this research via the use of frequency and mean distributions. Most of the farmers chosen are above the age of sixty-one (61) (40.67% of the total), as seen by the frequency distribution of their ages. Based on the findings, it is clear that the farmers' multi-purpose cooperative cannot afford to back the agricultural project of the participating farmers. The research concluded that fewer children should be born into existing families.

Cooperative society's effect on boosting SMEs in Ekiti State, Nigeria, was studied by Adegoke, Ajayi, and Ajayi (2021). The empirical research used Descriptive and Linear Regression Analysis. SME's were used as the dependent variable, with Loan Expansion, Financial Regulation, and Cooperative Society as the independent variables. The research showed that financial regulation has a detrimental effect on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), whereas loan extension and cooperative societies had beneficial effects. The research concluded that the best way to help small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) was for the government to make it easier for them to get loans under less rigorous conditions.

Specifically, Ogunmuyiwa, Oluwasanya, and Aladegoroye (2021) looked at how the participation rate of cooperative members affected the success of Nigerian small businesses. Existing Doings: Researchers have hitherto ignored the participation rate of cooperative and thrift society members in favor of examining the connection between cooperative and thrift societies and the success of small businesses. Participants were members of six (6) cooperatives and thrifts in the Ifo, Ewekoro, Obafemi/Owode, Abeokuta North, Abeokuta South, and Odeda LGAs of the Ogun Central Senatorial District. A total of 4,836 members of cooperative societies throughout the Six (6) Local Government Areas were used to determine the study's sample size of 369. All of the hypotheses were tested at a 5% threshold of significance with the use of descriptive statistics (DS) and Ordinary Least Square (OLS). The findings indicated that FIS significantly influenced the performance of small businesses ($= 0.4131$; $t_c = 5.7988$; $p 0.05$). Non-Financial Services (NFIS) also have a statistically significant impact on SME productivity ($= 0.2708$; $t_c = 3.2023$; $p 0.05$). There is a statistically significant relationship between SEF/MEM membership and SME performance ($= 0.1817$; $t_c = 2.6416$; $p 0.05$). There is a statistically significant relationship between patronage (PAT) and the success of local businesses ($= 0.7919$; $t_c = 15.8113$; $p 0.05$). Research indicates that FIS, NFIS, SEF/MEM, and PAT all significantly affect the success of Nigerian small enterprises. As a result, these criteria are the most important ones impacting the success and expansion of small enterprises in Nigeria.

Adekunle, Ola, Ogunrinade, and Odebunmi (2021) conducted an in-depth analysis of the roles cooperative societies in Osun state played in boosting the development of small and medium-sized enterprises. In order to explain "what" and "how," rather than only anticipate "what," the study opted for a qualitative research approach using an in-depth exploratory methodology. To investigate how cooperative societies influence the development of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Osun State, Nigeria, a comparative multiple case study was used because of the tight linkages it provides between empirical data and existing theories. Researchers chose to examine four different cooperatives. According to the results, cooperative societies in Osun State are crucial to the development of small and medium-sized enterprises. The research finds that the engagement of cooperative societies in the provision of micro loans to members for investment purpose in the field of firm development and growth is encouraging and should be perpetuated to increase the prosperity of persons in Osun State. It was suggested that cooperative society advocates in the State and Nigeria should continue and ramp up their work to help small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) succeed by making more resources available to its members.

Amusat, Alasiri, Sannie, Sanyaolu, Olawore, and Oyeleye (2022) looked at the feasibility of restructuring cooperative societies to increase social and economic advantages and foster entrepreneurship. 316 cooperatives in the Ikeja and Lagos Island local government and its LCDAs in Lagos State were surveyed using a descriptive and survey design. The study's samples were selected at random. Regression analysis in SPSS version 23 was used to test hypotheses, and descriptive statistics were provided in the form of frequency tables and percentages to illustrate the collected data. Cooperative members are confident that an easily accessible connecting road and reliable electricity supply will help their company succeed, according to the results. As an added bonus, sustainable development, which is highly sought after, may be aided by relaxed rules. In order to maximize the cooperatives' potential for social good and economic growth, the government and relevant stakeholders must devise a comprehensive and practical strategy for the sector. Therefore, it was suggested that the government provide cooperatives with financial, moral, institutional, and an operational environment conducive to achieving meaningful restructuring and the much-desired growth of entrepreneurship.

3.0 Methodology

Area of the Study

Ekiti State is the focus of this research. There are many states in Nigeria's Southwest area, including Ekiti State, which was officially recognized as such on October 1, 1996, by the military administration of the time, led by General Sani Abacha. There are now 16 LGAs and 3 senatorial districts in Ekiti State. The Ado municipal government serves as a case study for this investigation.

Research Design

The descriptive research design is used in this study. Descriptive study design is a scientific approach that entails monitoring and describing a subject's behavior without altering it in any manner.

Population of the Study

All of the micro, small, and medium-sized businesses in Ekiti State made comprised the study's population. SMEDAN reports that there are more than 400 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ado-Ekiti State (2021). Therefore, the research included both legally and illegally operating small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State.

Sampling and Sample Technique

Based on the account of SMEs in Ado-Ekiti, the study employed purposive sampling technique to select 50 operating SMEs into varied business activities in Ado-Ekiti. Hence, the selected 50 respondent were the target sample size attached to the study.

Research Instrument

The study's primary data came from a questionnaire with a clear framework and six distinct parts. The researcher constructed the questions using a Likert scale, ordering the options from least to most preferred.

Model Specification

Basically, the study adopted the model employed by Ogunmuyiwa, Oluwasanya and Aladegoroye (2021) on cooperative society and business performance in Nigeria. The author's model was clearly stated as:

$$SSBP = f(\text{FIS, NFIS, MEM, PAT})$$

1

Where:

SSBP = Small Business Performance

FIS = Financial Service of Cooperative Societies

NFIS = Non-financial Service of Cooperative Societies

MEM = Membership

PAT = Patronage of Cooperative Societies

By applying econometrics, the model is restated as:

$$SSBP = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1\text{FIS} + \alpha_2\text{NFIS} + \alpha_3\text{MEM} + \alpha_4\text{PAT} + \mu$$

2

Where:

α_0 = Constant

$\alpha_1 = \alpha_4$ = Coefficients of parameters that was estimated

Analytical Techniques

To achieve the stated objectives, multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the degree of connectivity between the independent variable (cooperative financial services, non-financial services, membership, patronage) and the dependent variable (SMEs) in Ekiti State.

4.0 Results and Discussion

The data were analyzed in testing the research hypotheses with the aim of achieving the objectives specified in the study. The research hypotheses were tested at 5% level of significance using inferential statistics involving regression analysis. Notably, the fifty returned questionnaires were coded and interpreted in this study.

Result of Hypotheses

Hypotheses denote that financial services, non-financial services, membership and patronage have not significantly contributed to small and medium scale enterprises in Ekiti State.

Table 1: Regression analysis showing the effect of financial services, non-financial services, membership and patronage on small and medium scale enterprises in Ekiti State.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.241	.372		6.023	.000
	Financial services	.146	.178	.117	4.818	.001
	Non-Financial services	.274	.159	.246	4.716	.003
	Membership	.149	.189	.115	3.791	.003
	Patronage	.283	.165	.242	3.709	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Small and Medium Scale business

Source: SPSS

From the Table 1, the following regression equation was established

$$SME = 2.241 + 0.146_{FIS} + 0.274_{NFIS} + 0.149_{MEM} + 0.283_{PAT}$$

According to the results of the regression analysis, the explanatory variables as expressed by FIS, NFIS, MEM, and PAT have a positive and significant effect on small and medium-sized businesses. This means that an increase in the value of FIS, NFIS, MEM, or PAT will result in a 14.6%, 27.4%, 14.9%, or 28.3% increase in small and medium-sized businesses. As a result of these results, it is clear that cooperative society characteristics have a beneficial and statistically significant impact on SMEs in Ekiti State.

Table 2: Result of Regression Analysis

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.888 ^a	.783	.623	.498
a. Predictors: (Constant), Financial services, non-financial services, Membership, Patronage				

Source: SPSS

Table 2 shows that there was a correlation of 0.888 between the independent variable (the number of cooperative societies) and the dependent variable (the number of cooperative societies) (Small and medium scale enterprise). $R^2 = 0.783$ ($P = 0.00$ 0.05), indicating that the independent variable was responsible for 78% of the variation in the dependent variable (Small and medium-sized business) (Cooperative societies). The modified R^2 value demonstrated the true importance of the independent variable (Cooperative societies) in explaining the dependent variable (Small and medium scale enterprise). This means that the explanatory factors accounted for around 62.3% of the total variance in the dependent variable. Explanatory power of the independent variable is high, as shown by the F value of 21.974, which is statistically significant at the.000 level. That the model is not affected by specification bias was shown here.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.505	4	2.376	21.974	.000 ^b
	Residual	8.575	45	.191		
	Total	10.080	49			
a. Dependent Variable: Small and medium scale business performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Financial services, non-financial services, Membership, Patronage						

Source: SPSS

The results of the ANOVA provide valuable insight into the model's efficacy. Table 4.6's results show that the F-test yields a value of 21.974, which is not statistically significant (P 0.05). As the resultant p-value of 0.00 was less than 0.05, the F-test is significant, and it follows that the regression model was well-fit. As a result, the research concludes that the alternative hypothesis, that Cooperative Societies have a major influence on SME's in Ekiti State, is true.

Discussion of Finding

Our study analyzed the effects of cooperative societies on MSMEs in Ekiti state. The study set out to answer four research questions and test two hypotheses on how best to do this. At the 5% significance level, the research hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics such multiple regression analysis.

Study results corroborated the key premise that access to financial services greatly boosted SME output. This study confirms previous research that found a robust correlation between microcredits, loans, and the growth of SMEs. Akerele and Adekunmbi (2018), on the other hand, claimed that the cooperative society's financial services had a negligible effect on the success of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs). Additional evidence demonstrated that non-financial services do have an effect on SMB output. This result lends credibility to the results of Ohen et al. (2018), Ademilua (2017), and Effiom (2014), all of whom concluded that the non-financial services provided by cooperative societies had a significant impact on the performance of small and medium-sized firms. Dunggio and Yasa (2016) argued that SMEs couldn't benefit from using non-financial services, however this study found the opposite to be true. And the data showed that being a member made a big difference in how well the small businesses did. This result supports the conclusion drawn by Kyazze et al. (2017), who found that a company's performance as a SME is impacted by its membership in a cooperative society. In contrast, Okoli (2018) found no connection between cooperative society membership and the prosperity of SMEs. The results backed up the claims made by Ogunmuyiwa et al., who discovered that customer loyalty significantly contributed to a company's success (2021).

5.0 Conclusion

This research aimed to determine the impact that cooperative societies have on the success of medium and small businesses in Ekiti State. In line with these findings, the research suggests that patronage and non-financial services are the most important characteristics of cooperative society in determining the success of small-scale businesses in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Therefore, both small firms and SMEs in general may exploit the cooperative characteristics explored in this research to their advantage. Accordingly, the findings corroborated the empirical finding of Ogunmuyiwa et al. (2021) that the presence of a cooperative society significantly affects the commercial performance of small and medium-sized firms in Ekiti State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on are finding:

- i. To improve company growth and foster entrepreneurial development, small firms should be encouraged to join or create cooperative societies to enable access to financing and equally take use of other features and possibilities given by cooperative societies.
- ii. To maximize the potential for financial and non-financial aid from the government and other organizations, agricultural cooperative societies should welcome their involvement.
- iii. Based on the results of the research, microfinance institutions and other financial institutions that provide assistance to cooperative societies should raise the size of the fund base allocated to cooperatives at a rate of interest that is both reasonable and manageable.

6.0 References

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